

Studies on Hydrofluorene Derivatives—Part I. Syntheses of 1, 6- and 1, 7-Dimethyl- and 7-Hydroxy-1-methylfluorenes

Kalpana Das Gupta

Syntheses of 1,6-dimethylfluorene, 1,7-dimethylfluorene and 7-hydroxy-1-methylfluorene have been described.

Gibberellins¹, metabolites of *Gibberella fujikuroi* are known to be powerful physiologically active phytohormones. Gibberellic acid, the most important member of this tetracyclic diterpenoid group, afforded gibberene² and fluorenol³ on extensive degradation and

CHART I

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2. T. Yabuta, Y. Sumiki, Azabu, T. Tamara, H. Igarashi and K. Tamari, *J. Agric. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1940, 16, 975.
3. T. P. C. Mulholland, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2693.

these were shown to be identical with 1,7-dimethylfluorene (VII)⁴ and 7-hydroxy-1-methylfluorene (XI)⁵ respectively. In the present communication, syntheses of (VII) and (XI) have been described through an entirely different route. A synthesis of 1,6-dimethylfluorene (XIII) has also been achieved. The starting material in this synthetic project was 2-bromo-4-methylindan-1-one⁶. It was condensed with ethyl malonate to afford ethyl (1-oxo-4-methylindanyl-2-)malonate (I, R = C₂H₅). Hydrolysis of (I) was carried out with methanolic potassium hydroxide solution and the resulting dicarboxylic acid was decarboxylated to furnish 2-carboxymethyl-4-methyl-1-oxoindane (II, R = H) and this was esterified to give the keto ester (II, R = CH₃). The keto ester (II, R = CH₃) was subjected to Stobbe condensation with dimethyl succinate⁷⁻⁹ and the product, on esterification afforded the unsaturated trimethyl ester (III); λ max 268 m μ . On the basis of the UV spectrum and from previous analogy^{9,10}, the endocyclic position of the double bond as depicted in (III) is preferred. The ester (III) was hydrolysed and decarboxylated^{9,11} in one step to afford the acid (IV, R = H)

CHART II

4. T. P. C. Mulholland and G. Ward, *ibid.*, 1954, 4676.
5. A Morrison and T. P. C. Mulholland, *ibid.*, 1958, 2703.
6. Y. Kos and H. J. E. Lowenthal, *ibid.*, 1963, 605.
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9. B. K. Bhattacharyya, A. K. Bose, A. Chatterjee and (late) B. P. Sen, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1964, **41**, 479.
10. A. Chatterjee and S. Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1964, **41**, 643.
11. S. K. Gupta, A. Chatterjee, (late) B. P. Sen and B. K. Bhattacharyya, *ibid.*, 1958, **35**, 751.

which on esterification furnished the ester (IV, R = CH₃). The endocyclic structure assigned to compounds (IV, R = H or R = CH₃) is supported by the observations of Clemo¹² and of Turner and Garner¹³, and confirmed by the absence of vinyl proton in NMR spectrum of the acid (IV, R = H). The ester (IV, R = CH₃) was catalytically hydrogenated to 2-methoxycarbonylmethyl-3 β -methoxycarbonylethyl-7-methylindane (V, R = CH₃) and the latter hydrolysed to the acid (V, R = H). The acid (V, R = H) on pyrolysis with lead carbonate afforded the ketone (VI). This was subjected to Grignard reaction with methylmagnesium iodide and the product on dehydration with toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid and dehydrogenation with Pd/C (10%) afforded 1,7-dimethylfluorene (VII). The ester (IV, R = CH₃) on Dieckmann cyclisation afforded 6-methoxycarbonyl-7-oxo-1-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrofluorene (VIII). Placing of the double bond in (VIII) is based on the observation of Ingold¹⁴. The

β -keto ester (VIII) was smoothly aromatised⁹ with methanolic hydrochloric acid to afford the ester (IX, R = CH₃). The ester (IX, R = CH₃) on hydrolysis afforded the acid (IX, R = H) which on decarboxylation with quinoline and copper bronze furnished 7-hydroxy-1-methylfluorene (XI). The ketonic cleavage^{8,9} of the β -keto ester (VIII) was carried out under controlled acidic condition to furnish a mixture of ketones (double bond isomers) as is evident from its U.V. spectra. The mixture of the ketones (X) was aromatised with Pd/C

Chart IV

12. G. R. Clemo, L. H. Groves, L. Munday and G. A. Swan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 863.

13. R. B. Turner and R. H. Garner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **80**, 1424.

14. "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry" by C. K. Ingold, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, p. 562 (1953).

(30%) to give (XI). The β -keto ester (VIII) was alkylated to give (XII, R = CH₃); the crude alkylated product on acidic hydrolysis furnished 1,6-dimethylfluorene (XIII). The above mechanism may be postulated for the elimination of ketonic oxygen leading to (XIII). An authentic sample of (XIII) was prepared from 2-*p*-methylbenzyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-3-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (XIV, R = CO₂C₂H₅). This on hydrolysis and subsequent decarboxylation gave (XIV, R = H). This was next subjected to catalytic hydrogenation in presence of Pd/C (10%) to afford the saturated compound (XV). Polyphosphoric acid cyclisation of (XV) gave 1,6-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofluorene (XVI) which on catalytic dehydrogenation in presence of Pd/C (10%) afforded (XIII).

EXPERIMENTAL *

Diethyl (1-oxo-4-methylindanyl-2-)-malonate (I, R = C₂H₅).—Diethyl sodio malonate was prepared from sodium dust (4 g.) under dry benzene (445 ml.) containing absolute ethanol (1 ml.). To this was added dropwise a solution of 2-bromo-4-methylindan-1-one (25 g.) dissolved in benzene (35 ml.). The reaction mixture was shaken and externally cooled. It was then heated under reflux for 15 hr. and the product worked up to afford (I), b.p. 175°/0.4 m.m. (26.7 g.; 79%). (Found: C, 66.8; H, 6.7. Calc. for C₁₇H₂₀O₅; C, 67.1; H, 6.6%).

2-Methoxycarbonylmethyl-4-methyl-1-oxoindane (II, R = CH₃).—A solution of the preceding ester (I, 10 g.) and methanolic potassium hydroxide solution (80 ml.; 20%) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. Methanol was distilled off and the residue on dilution with water was extracted with ether. The acidic product (7.5 g.) obtained after removal of the solvent was decarboxylated by heating at 185–195° for ½ hr. in an oil bath. On cooling, 2-carboxymethyl-4-methyl-1-oxoindane (6.9 g.) was obtained and had m.p. 133–135° (Lit. m.p. 137°). The acid (10 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of sulphuric acid (3 ml.) and methanol (45 ml.) for 12 hr. to furnish the ester (II, 9.7 g.), m.p. 80–81° (Lit. m.p. 84.5–85°) (Found: C, 71.3; H, 6.1. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₄O₃; C, 71.5; H, 6.4%).

1- α,β -bis (Methoxycarbonyl)ethylidene-2 α -methoxycarbonylmethyl-4-methylindene (III).—To a stirred suspension of potassium *t*-butoxide, prepared from potassium (3.4 g.) in *t*-butanol (35 ml.), dimethyl succinate (17 g.) was added dropwise under nitrogen and at room temperature. The resulting yellow homogeneous mixture was then added to a well-stirred solution of the keto ester (II, 12.6 g.) in *t*-butanol rapidly. The reaction mixture turned deep red. It was stirred for 2 hr. more and the reaction allowed to proceed at room temperature under nitrogen for 16 hr. without stirring. On working up the reaction mixture, a dark orange gummy acidic product (14.6 g.) was obtained and it was esterified with a mixture of sulphuric acid (20 ml.) and methanol (150 ml.). The reaction mixture was worked up to furnish the *trimethyl ester (III)*, b.p. 197°/0.4 m.m. (7.8 g.; 51%); λ , max 272m μ (log ϵ 4.1). (Found: C, 66.3; H, 7.1. Calc. for C₁₉H₂₂O₆; C, 65.9; H, 6.4%). The unchanged keto ester (2.9 g.) was recovered.

* All m.p.s. and b.p.s. are uncorrected. The U.V. spectra were recorded in the Unicam Spectro photometer S.P. 500 for alcoholic solutions, if not mentioned otherwise. N.M.R. data was recorded in diuteriochloroform solution in A 60 Varian Instrument with TMS as internal standard.

2-Carboxymethyl-3 β -carboxyethyl-7-methylindene (IV, R = H).—The ester (III, 12.5 g.) was heated under reflux with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (175 ml.), hydrobromic acid (115 ml.; 48%) and water (60 ml.) for 7 hr. Lower boiling acids were distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue diluted with water. It was extracted with ether and the acidic material was taken up with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The alkaline extract was acidified with cold hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The acid, obtained on removal of the solvent, was purified by recrystallisation from dilute ethanol (8.6 g.; 92%), m.p. 199–201°; λ max 262 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2). (Found : C, 69.3; H, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$; C, 69.2; H, 6.1%). NMR spectrum consisted of the following peaks, 7.66 (singlet, methyl on benzene ring, 6.6 (singlet, benzylic methylene); 6.49 (singlet, methylene in 2 position of indene nucleus) and τ , 2.83 (characteristic multiplet, aromatic protons).

2-Methoxycarbonylmethyl-3 β -methoxycarbonylethyl-7-methylindene (IV, R = CH₃).—The above acid (IV, R = H; 8 g.) was esterified with a mixture of sulphuric acid (4 ml.) and methanol (50 ml.) by heating under reflux for 20 hr; the reaction product on usual working up afforded the dimethyl ester (IV). It was recrystallised from dilute ethanol and had m.p. 44–46° (7.3 g.; 82%); λ max 258 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1). (Found : C, 70.9; H, 7.2. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ C, 70.8; H, 6.9%).

2-Methoxycarbonylmethyl-3 β -methoxycarbonylethyl-7-methylindane (V, R = CH₃).—The unsaturated diester (IV, R = CH₃; 5.7 g.) in ethanol (20 ml.) was hydrogenated over palladium-on-asbestos (0.3 g.; 5%). The catalyst was filtered off and the residue, left after removal of the solvent, was distilled at 172°/0.4 m.m. to furnish the saturated diester (V, R = CH₃; 5 g.; 84%). (Found : C, 70.4; H, 7.8. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$ C, 70.3; H, 7.6%).

2-Carboxymethyl-3 β -carboxyethyl-7-methylindane (V, R = H).—(A) The ester (V, R = CH₃; 0.5 g.) was saponified with methanolic potassium hydroxide solution (3.5 ml.; 10%) by heating under reflux for 4 hr. The acidic material thus obtained was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60–80°), and had m.p. 185–187° (0.42 g.; 93%). (Found : C, 68.7; H, 7.1. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{18}O_4$; C, 68.7; H, 6.9%).

(B) The ester (V, R = CH₃; 0.5 g.) was hydrolysed with a refluxing mixture of glacial acetic acid (5 ml.) and hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) for 10 hr. On usual work up, the acid, m.p. 185–187° (0.36 g.; 80%) was obtained. The m.p. remained undepressed on admixture with that described before.

8-Methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4,4a,9a-hexahydrofluorene (VI).—An intimate mixture of the dibasic acid (V, R = H; 0.7 g.) and lead carbonate (2.1 g.) was introduced, under nitrogen, into a preheated electrical chamber and the temperature was raised to 295–310° and maintained at that temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. whereupon a yellowish distillate was obtained. The product was taken in ether and the ethereal solution washed with sodium carbonate solution (5%) and water respectively and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue left after removal of the solvent was distilled at 100°/0.3 m.m. to afford the ketone (VI) (0.32 g.; 60%); λ max 250 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0). (Found : C, 84.1; H, 8.2. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{16}O$; C, 83.9; H, 8.1%). The *semi-carbazone* (methanol) melted at 210–211° (decomp.). (Found : C, 69.9; H, 7.7; N, 16.2. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{19}ON_3$; C, 70.0; H, 7.4; N, 16.3%). The *2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* (benzene and methanol) melted at 177–178°. (Found : C, 63.2; H, 5.3; N, 14.7. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_4$; C, 63.4; H, 5.5; N, 14.7%).

1,7-Dimethylfluorene (VII).—To a well-stirred Grignard reagent, prepared from methyl iodide (2.1 ml.) and magnesium (0.21 g.) in dry ether (30 ml.), was added dropwise the ketone (VI, 0.7 g.) in dry ether (75 ml.) with cooling. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 hr. and left for 2 hr. at room temperature. It was next heated under reflux for 1 hr. The product was cooled and decomposed with ammonium chloride (0.5 g.) and worked up in the usual way to afford a brown coloured oil (0.84 g.). This was dehydrated by heating with toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (0.6 g.) in dry benzene (90 ml.) and the water formed in the reaction was removed as azeotrope with benzene. The contents of the flask were taken in ether and washed with water. On removal of the solvent a brown-coloured oil was obtained which was subjected to evaporative distillation at 82°/0.3 m.m. to afford a colourless oil (0.4 g.). It gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane. This (0.4 g.) was dehydrogenated with Pd/C (0.2 g.; 10%) by heating at 280–300° for 1½ hr. under nitrogen. The crude hydrocarbon was purified by chromatography over alumina (11 g.) using petroleum (b.p. 60–80°):benzene (1 : 10) as eluent. It was then recrystallised from methanol and then finally subjected to sublimation to afford the pure compound (0.3 g.; 91%), m.p. 108–108.5° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 108–108.5°); λ max 270 m μ (log ϵ 4.5), 297 m μ (log ϵ 3.9) and 304 m μ (log ϵ 3.9). (Found : C, 92.8; H, 7.4. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄, C, 92.8; H, 7.3%). The hydrocarbon furnished 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone complex (benzene), m.p. 160–161° (35 mg.; 90%). (Found : C, 65.9; H, 3.9. Calc. for C₂₈H₁₉O₇N₃; C, 66.0; H, 3.7%).

6-Methoxycarbonyl-7-oxo-1-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrofluorene (VIII).—The unsaturated dimethyl ester (IV, R = CH₃; 3 g.) in thiophene-free benzene (15 ml.) was subjected to Dieckmann cyclisation by heating under reflux in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 2½ hr. with a solution of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (0.5 g.) and methanol (0.8 ml.). It was next cooled and acidified with ice-cold hydrochloric acid (2 ml.; dil.). On usual work up, a brown-coloured oil was obtained which solidified on trituration with methanol. The β -keto ester thus obtained was purified by evaporative distillation at 100°/0.05 m.m. followed by crystallisation from methanol (2.2 g.; 85%), m.p. 110–112°, λ max 249 m μ (log ϵ 4.3). It gave green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 74.8; H, 6.0. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₆O₃; C, 74.9; H, 6.3%).

6-Methoxycarbonyl-7-hydroxy-1-methylfluorene (IX, R = CH₃).—To a solution of the β -keto ester (VIII; 0.2 g.) in methanol (7 ml.) was added hydrochloric acid (2–3 drops; conc.) and the resulting homogeneous solution was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight whereupon colourless long needles separated. These were filtered and washed with methanol. The combined washings and the mother liquor were concentrated, treated with one drop of hydrochloric acid (conc.) and the whole left for 4 days. It was diluted with water and on working up, afforded a solid which was mixed up with the aforementioned crystals. This crude product was purified by crystallisation from methanol to afford the desired hydroxy ester (IX, 0.14 g.; 88%), m.p. 142–143°; λ max 248 m μ (log ϵ 4.5), 272 m μ (log ϵ 4.3) and 288 m μ (log ϵ 4.2). It furnished green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 75.4; H, 5.8. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₄O₃; C, 75.6; H, 5.6%).

6-Carboxy-7-hydroxy-1-methylfluorene (IX, R = H).—A solution of the above phenolic ester (IX, 0.5 g.) and methanolic potassium hydroxide solution, prepared from potassium hydroxide (1 g.) in methanol (15 ml.), was heated under reflux for 4 hr. The desired acid

thus obtained was purified by recrystallisation from ether-benzene (0.34 g.; 68%), and had m.p. 280–282° (decomp.); λ_{\max} 282 m μ (log ϵ 4.3) and 325 m μ (log ϵ 4.5). It gave light-green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 74.9; H, 5.4. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₂O₃; C, 74.9; H, 5.0%).

1. *Methyl-7-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrofluorene* (X).—To a solution of the β -keto ester (VIII; 0.7 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) was added aqueous sulphuric acid (4.5 ml.; 7.5%) and the homogeneous reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 3½ hr. under nitrogen. The colour of the reaction mixture gradually turned red. It was worked up in the usual way to afford an oil which solidified on scratching. The pure ketone (X) was obtained on crystallisation from methanol, and had m.p. 107–108° (0.42 g.; 84%); λ_{\max} 254 m μ (log ϵ 4.0) and 262 m μ (log ϵ 3.9). It gave no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 84.7; H, 7.0. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄O; C, 84.8; H, 7.1%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (benzene), m.p. 209° (decomp.). Found : N, 14.8. Calc. for C₂₀H₁₈O₄N₄; N, 14.7%).

7-Hydroxy-1-methylfluorene (XI).—(A) A mixture of the α , β - and β , γ -unsaturated ketones (X, 0.5 g.) in dry xylene (15 ml.) and Pd/C (0.2 g.; 30%) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. under nitrogen. It was cooled and left overnight under nitrogen. The catalyst was filtered off and the solvent removed. The crude compound thus obtained was crystallised from xylene-petroleum (b.p. 60–80°), and had m.p. 166–168° (Lit.⁵ m.p. 166–168°); (0.4 g.; 80%); λ_{\max} 274 m μ (log ϵ 4.2), 283 m μ (log ϵ 4.2), 308 m μ (log ϵ 3.9) and 314 m μ (log ϵ 3.7). It did not furnish any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 75.4; H, 6.3. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₂O, C, 85.7; H, 6.2%).

(B) A mixture of the phenolic acid (IX, R = H; 0.2 g.), freshly distilled quinoline (4 ml.) and copper bronze (0.1 g.) was heated in an oil bath (220–230°) for 1 hr. under nitrogen. The reaction mixture was next heated under reflux for 1 hr. (250–260°) under nitrogen. It was cooled and acidified carefully with dil. HCl and the copper bronze was filtered off. The filtrate was washed thoroughly with HCl (6N) and the brown-coloured oil obtained on removal of the solvent was sublimed at 115–120°/0.2 mm. to afford a pale yellow solid. It was recrystallised from xylene-petroleum ether (60–80°) to afford star-shaped crystals of (XI), m.p. 166–168° (0.2 g.; 87%). The mixed m.p. remained undepressed on admixture with that of the hydroxy compound (XI) described under (A).

The *methyl ether* of (XI) was prepared by heating the above phenol under reflux with methyl-iodide in dry acetone and anhyd. potassium carbonate. This was crystallised from methanol, and had m.p. 112–113° (Lit.⁵ m.p. 111–112.5°). The mixed m.p. remained undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample. The *acetate* was prepared by treating the phenol with acetyl chloride in dry pyridine and the product was crystallised from methanol, and melted at 131–132° (Lit.⁵ m.p. 131–132°). Found : C, 80.5; H, 6.3. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₄O₂; C, 80.7; H, 5.9%).

1,6-Dimethylfluorene (XIII).—A solution of the β -keto ester (VIII, 0.8 g.) in dry benzene (15 ml.) was added dropwise in the cold to a suspension of sodium dust (0.1 g.) under dry benzene (20 ml.) with gentle stirring under nitrogen. It was stirred for 6 hr. after the formation of the salt and the whole left overnight at room temperature under nitrogen. Methyl iodide (1.5 g.) was next added and the reaction mixture heated under reflux for 8 hr. under

nitrogen. A dark-brown coloured oil was obtained on usual work-up and this was evaporatively distilled at $140^{\circ}/0.2$ mm. to afford a pale-yellow oil (0.5 g.). The alkylated ester (XII) thus obtained was heated under reflux for 6 hr. with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (4.6 ml.), hydrobromic acid (2.3 ml.) and water (0.5 ml.) under nitrogen. The yellowish solid obtained on working up the reaction mixture was chromatographed over activated alumina (10 g.) using petroleum (b.p. $60-80^{\circ}$)-benzene as the eluting solvent. It was next recrystallised from methanol to give colourless flakes, m.p. $152-154^{\circ}$ (0.4 g.; 63%); λ max 212 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.6), 269 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.3), 274 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2), 280 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.5), 290 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.7) and 302 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.8). (Found : C, 92.7; H, 7.2. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{14}$; C, 92.8; H, 7.3%). The 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone complex (benzene) was prepared as dark-red needles, m.p. $182-184^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 66.1; H, 4.0. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{19}O_7N_3$; C, 66.0; H, 3.7%).

2-p-Methylbenzyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-3-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (XIV, $R = CO_2C_2H_5$).—To a cooled thick suspension of potassium *t*-butoxide, prepared from potassium (5 g.) in *t*-butanol, Hagemann's ester (23 g.) was added. *p*-Xylylbromide (24 g.) was next added to the reaction mixture portionwise and the reaction mixture heated under reflux for 15 hr. It was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue obtained on removal of the solvent was distilled at $198-200^{\circ}/0.4$ mm. to give the desired condensation product (XIV; 23 g.; 64%); λ max $240-242$ $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0). (Found : C, 75.8; H, 7.8. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{22}O_3$; C, 75.5; H, 7.7%).

2-p-Methylbenzyl-3-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (XIV, $R = H$).—The keto ester (XIV, 19.6 g.) was hydrolysed and simultaneously decarboxylated by heating under reflux with a mixture of potassium hydroxide (15 g.), water (15 ml.) and absolute alcohol (105 ml.) for 30 hr. On cooling and acidifying with cold hydrochloric acid (6N), the reaction mixture was extracted with ether. The solvent washed successively with brine, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, brine and water and finally dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue obtained after removal of the solvent was distilled at $132-134^{\circ}/0.4$ mm. to give the desired compound (XV, $R = H$); (5.6 g.; 73%); λ max $240-242$ $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0). (Found : C, 87.0; H, 8.5. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{18}O$; C, 87.1; H, 8.5%).

2-p-Methylbenzyl-3-methylcyclohexanone (XV).—The compound (XIV, $R = H$; 5 g.) in ethanol (25 ml.) was catalytically hydrogenated with Pd/C (0.3 g., 10%). The catalyst was filtered off and the residue, obtained after removal of the solvent was distilled at $125^{\circ}/0.2$ mm. (5 g.; 95%); λ max 266 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.3) and 275 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.8); ν_{CHCl_3} max 1710 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 83.3; H, 9.0. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{20}O$; C, 83.3; H, 9.3%).

1,6-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofluorene (XVI).—To a well-stirred homogeneous solution of polyphosphoric acid, prepared from *o*-phosphoric acid (9 ml., 89%) and phosphorus pentoxide (15 g.), the compound (XV, 1.5 g.) was added and the whole heated at $80-90^{\circ}$ for 2 hr. with stirring. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed with ice and water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water respectively and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue obtained on removal of the solvent was distilled at $114-118^{\circ}/0.2$ mm. (0.5 g.; 55%); λ max 267 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2). (Found : C, 91.0; H, 8.9. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{18}$; C, 90.9; H, 9.1).

1,6-Dimethylfluorene (XIII).—The cyclisation product (XVI; 1 g.) was dehydrogenated with Pd/C (0.1 g.; 10%) by heating on a metal bath (180–190°) for 26 hr. The catalyst was filtered off and the solvent washed with water. The yellowish solid obtained after removal of the solvent was purified by chromatography over activated alumina (24 g.) using petroleum (b.p. 60–80°) as the eluting solvent. It was finally purified by crystallisation from methanol to afford the hydrocarbon (XIII), m.p. 152–154° (75 mg.; 77%); λ max 270 m μ (log ϵ 4.4) and 300 m μ (log ϵ 4.3). (Found: C, 92.8; H, 7.3. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄, C, 92.8; H, 7.3%). The mixed m.p. of this compound and the sample described earlier remained undepressed. The 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone complex, prepared in the usual way melted at 182–184° (benzene). The mixed m.p. of this compound with that of the same derivative described earlier remained undepressed.

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Department of Organic Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Jadavpur, Calcutta-32.

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